

Teaching speech in the process of teaching literacy

MATYAQUBOVA FOTIMA URINBAYEVNA
URGANCH DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI TALABASI

Abstract: This scientific article describes the methodology and skills of speech development in the process of teaching literacy.

Key words: speech, skills, methodology, language, speech skills.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada savod o'rgatish jarayonida nutq o'stirish metodikasi hamda ko'nikmalari haqida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq, ko'nikma, metodika, til, nutqiy ko'nikma.

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The main content of the speech development methodology is the formation of children's oral speech, speech communication with others, and their skills. The methodology of speech development allows you to find answers to the following main questions: what to teach (how to educate children's speech skills), how to teach (in what conditions, which methods and methods should be used in the formation of children's speech), why exactly this kind of teaching is necessary (the proposed methods of speech development are based on the data of theory and practice). In the theory of speech development methodology, all the positive results

created in the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad and currently available in the field of speech development methodology, reflecting the objective features of teaching children's mother tongue, are summarized. The theory of speech development methodology is developing together with methodical practice. The viability of some methodical rules is being checked in practice, the practice itself is setting important goals for the science that have not yet found their solution. An educator who does not know the methodological theory blindly educates children based on his own assumptions or copying the experiences of others. He misses many things, because he does not know various methods and techniques.

The methodology of speech development is based on the basic rules of psycholinguistics. His basic rule that language serves as a communication tool in all spheres of human activity is considered as a program rule in the methodology of speech development. Therefore, it is aimed at equipping with knowledge and skills related to the development of speech.

Speech development is a very complex, multifactorial process of mastering the socio-historical experience that plays a central role in the individual psychological development of a child. It is not a social process. Work on the development of children's speech should be organized and carried out by a specialist who has good theoretical and practical experience, who has formed valuable relationships with children. The implementation of this goal involves solving the following tasks: formation of the ability to see and understand the features of speech development of preschool children at different age stages; taking

into account not only the child's age, but also his own characteristics, to influence his speech and teach him to choose the most effective way to cooperate with him, and to analyze the obtained results; knowledge of the specific methods and methods of developing various aspects of children's speech, as well as their application and mastery in the context of didactic speech communication; to stimulate the desire to create original methods and ways of influencing the speech of children of preschool age, based on the critical analysis of educational methodical manuals; in the process of learning the course, students need to master such concepts as the theoretical foundations of the speech development methodology and the psycholinguistic foundations of teaching children their mother tongue; mastering the basics of the methodology of applying them in practice based on the knowledge of the features of the development of the speech of children of primary and preschool age of the modern Uzbek language, the psycholinguistic and linguodidactic foundations of teaching the mother tongue; to acquire the ability and skills to learn logical and emotional expressiveness in reading and speech, to be able to analyze a work of art and know how to perform it, to develop children's vocabulary, to develop pronunciation skills, to form grammatically correct speech in order to establish their speech activity and master the skills of organizing communication of children with each other and with other persons.

Language makes it possible to plan mental activities. In this process, the important task of language is to control human behavior. School education begins

with teaching elementary reading and writing. Based on the "Alphabet", students are taught to read and write in a short period of time, then the reading and writing skills are improved, gradually turning into a skill, Reading and writing skill is a skill related to speech. Reading and writing skills are also related to other types of speech activity. An activity can be repeated several times for the formation of skills. Uzbek language script - phonetic script. In writing, the student performs the complex mental activity of turning sounds into letters, and in reading into sounds. Assuming that this activity occurs continuously, reading and writing are carried out in parallel. The Uzbek language script is a phonetic script. The Latin alphabet of 1993 was used as the basis for writing the Uzbek language. For each sound of speech, a corresponding form was adopted. In the process of teaching literacy, the teacher should take into account the phonetic features of the Uzbek language when informing students about sounds. Literacy is taught using the analytical-synthetic sound method. The word is divided into syllables, the required sound is extracted from the syllable, analyzed, and synthesized with the studied letter. Current Uzbek vowel system: a, o, o', u, i, e. In teaching literacy, introducing sounds and letters starts with vowels. The letter e- is written at the beginning of words and syllables instead of a middle wide unstressed vowel and after a consonant. In literacy education, the -e (ye) that comes at the beginning of the word and then the -e that comes after the consonant is taught. The letter -o represents the lower wide, labial - o sound in Uzbek words. in Russian international words, in an unstressed syllable, it is pronounced in the form of -a (kalkhoz), like the sound of -o (tonnna), and in

the form of short -i. Therefore, these vowel words are included in the educational process after the literacy period.

The Uzbek language has 24 consonants. 3 of them are letter combinations, 24 consonants are denoted by 23 consonants. The teaching of consonants is also based on a certain order and demand. The alphabet period begins with the teaching of sonorous (voiced) sounds. But the sonorous consonant -ng is taught after introducing the vowel letter n and g. Given the difficulty in teaching letter combinations, they are learned at the end of the alphabet period. The letter J represents two sounds, taking this into account, separate classes are held for it. In the process of teaching literacy, the use of 4 different versions of the letter (printed, written, uppercase and lowercase) is taught. Teaching students to read is carried out on the basis of syllables. If orthographic reading is used at the initial stage of reading, orthoepic teaching skills are gradually formed. In order to learn to read in syllables, it is important to divide the word into syllables, to identify the sound that forms a syllable, and to teach the difference between open and closed syllables.

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